

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF SLEEP FOR MAINTAINING THE ORGANISM'S HOMEOSTASIS

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Abstract

A review article examining the relationship between sleep, nutrition, and recovery processes, which is of great importance for the prevention of obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular and neuropsychiatric diseases, as well as for maintaining homeostasis.

Keywords: *sleep, phases and stages of sleep, stress factors, physiological processes, homeostasis*

THEORETICAL REVIEW OF THE ISSUE

The phenomenon of sleep and dreams, being a fundamental aspect of human life, continues to be the subject of intensive interdisciplinary research. Despite significant progress in understanding the neurophysiological basis of these states, their functional content, cognitive mechanisms, and the full range of relationships with mental activity have not yet received an exhaustive scientific interpretation.

The division of sleep into certain periods is quite fully reflected in scientific publications [1]. Sleep is divided into slow and fast phases, which cyclically replace each other approximately 5–6 times during the night. The phase of rapid eye movement (REM) sleep occurs after falling asleep. Its name appeared due to observation of the electroencephalogram: brain activity during this phase is similar to the state of wakefulness - heartbeat and breathing are accelerated, but muscle tone is almost absent. Due to this combination of brain activity and complete relaxation of the body, REM sleep is also called paradoxical. On the EEG at this time, desynchronization of rhythms is visible - slow waves are replaced by fast, low-amplitude ones. Rapid eye movements, uneven breathing, changes in pulse and involuntary contractions of small muscles are observed. Slow sleep (NREM) consists of three stages: drowsiness, light and deep sleep. The first stage (drowsiness) is the transition between wakefulness and sleep, when muscles gradually relax, body temperature, respiratory rate and heart rate decrease, which occurs under the influence of the vagus nerve. The second stage (light sleep) is characterized by theta waves on the EEG and the appearance of sleep spindles and K-complexes - short waves of activity, which are considered important for memory consolidation. During this period, breathing and heartbeat slow down, and the temperature drops even more. The third stage (deep sleep) is the period of delta waves (low-frequency and high-amplitude). This is the most restorative part of sleep: the body is maximally relaxed, and it is here that dreams can occur. The process of alternating REM and NREM phases of sleep is probably provided by a mechanism of mutual inhibition between groups of neurons in the brainstem. In particular, the activity of cholinergic

neurons, which increases during REM sleep, inhibits the work of noradrenergic and serotonergic neurons, and vice versa. This cyclical change in activity forms the characteristic structure of sleep with alternating phases. The leading role in sleep regulation belongs to emotions. With increased anxiety, emotional arousal or stress, cortisol secretion is activated, which suppresses melatonin production and disrupts the initiation of deep sleep phases.

Some studies [2] indicate a close connection between sleep paralysis and lucid dreams. According to scientists, both phenomena may have a common neurobiological nature. A key factor is a person's tendency to dissociative states - a feeling of detachment from reality in everyday life, which may increase the likelihood of both types of experiences during sleep. Lucid dreams and sleep paralysis are probably related due to the peculiarities of brain function.

In recent years, a series of studies on the impact of the environment on people's sleep and dreams has appeared [3]. Since the beginning of the full-scale war in Ukraine, the lifestyle of the population has undergone significant changes. The constant influence of stress factors, such as security threats, air raids, instability of living conditions and psycho-emotional stress, has led to a disruption of the usual rhythm of the day and a deterioration in the quality of sleep. During the war, sleep disorders become a common problem, reflecting the general level of adaptive stress of the body in conditions of prolonged stress. The authors determined the features of sleep disorders in civilians and military personnel during the Russian-Ukrainian war. The main attention was paid to the influence of the psychological trauma of war on the formation of sleep disorders. The study reveals the interdependence between anxiety and depressive disorders and the occurrence of chronic insomnia. Thus, sleep is considered not simply as an obligatory biological function, but as a complex mental process that shows the internal state of a person and the level of his emotional stability.

Studies [4] studied the peculiarities of the condition of the civilian population of Ukraine, which suffers from sleep disorders due to the influence of the surrounding circumstances of wartime. These sleep disorders lead to a deterioration in emotional health and an

increase in the level of psycho-emotional exhaustion under the influence of external stress factors. As part of the study, a questionnaire was conducted to assess the quality of sleep of respondents and identify factors that may negatively affect its duration and fullness. The results obtained indicate that a significant part of the respondents has sleep disorders of varying intensity.

Studies [5] show that the key consequence of martial law for mental health is the massive spread of anxiety and depression, which has been recorded since the beginning of 2022. Their chronicity, through psychosomatic mechanisms, triggers a cascade of other anxiety disorders, which directly affects the quality of sleep and, as a result, the mental component of the quality of life.

The results of the analysis of the dynamics of sleep disorders show that the greatest severity of problems with falling asleep, depth and restorative function of sleep is observed a month after the start of hostilities. By the 10th month, their intensity decreases, which corresponds to the resistance phase in the mechanisms of stress adaptation. However, after a year, the severity of the disorders increases again, which is regarded as a sign of the exhaustion phase in conditions of chronic stress. At the same time, it was found that after a year of war, mental quality of life remains low, but no longer correlates with sleep indicators.

A number of authors [6] have particularly carefully studied the impact of war on children's sleep. The data obtained confirm that prolonged psychoemotional stress significantly disrupts the normal architecture of sleep in children. The most common symptoms were difficulty falling asleep and frequent interruptions of sleep during the night. In addition, the development of more complex disorders, such as snoring, sleep apnea and various parasomnias, was recorded. Comparison with peacetime data demonstrates how the war changed the structure of sleep problems in healthy children. If in peacetime one of the key concerns was excessive daytime sleepiness, then during the war other disorders came to the fore: the frequency of early awakenings increased sharply, difficulties with falling asleep became much more common, and the number of complaints about snoring also increased. At the same time, phenomena such as nightmares remained at a consistently high level in both periods. These changes, according to the authors, vividly illustrate the profound impact of prolonged stress on the physiology of sleep in the child's body.

Traumatic experiences, anxiety about the future, and constant mental stress directly trigger a cascade of nighttime sleep disturbances. These include insomnia, fragmented sleep, trouble falling asleep, and recurring nightmares. [7]

Therefore, based on the above, we can conclude that sleep is one of the most sensitive systems of the body to the effects of war stress.

It is known that one of the key hormones that determines the sleep-wake cycle is melatonin. The maximum concentration of the hormone during the night promotes falling asleep. At the same time, there is a decrease in body temperature and a decrease in the activity of the sympathetic nervous system.

Another important hormone, cortisol, has the opposite secretion rhythm to melatonin. Its level is minimal during deep sleep and begins to increase in the second half of the night, reaching a peak in the morning. This contributes to awakening, mobilization of energy resources, and maintenance of glucose homeostasis.

As shown by a number of researchers [8], chronic sleep disturbances or changes in circadian rhythm can lead to increased evening cortisol levels, which is associated with stress, fatigue, and metabolic disorders.

It has also been found [9] that reduced sleep duration is associated with decreased insulin sensitivity and impaired glucose metabolism, leading to the development of insulin resistance. Insulin resistance affects both peripheral tissues and the liver: in the muscles, glucose uptake under the action of insulin decreases, and in the liver, glucose production itself increases. During sleep, the body uses a number of mechanisms to maintain a stable glucose level during the period of nocturnal fasting. Glucose utilization is highest during wakefulness and lowest in the phases of slow sleep, while during fast sleep it has intermediate values.

It has been shown [10] that in healthy people, glucose tolerance varies during the day: the plasma response to glucose administration is significantly higher in the evening than in the morning, and the lowest at night. The decrease in the body's ability to absorb glucose in the evening is partly due to a decrease in tissue sensitivity to insulin and a weakening of the insulin response to an increase in glucose levels. In the first half of the night, glucose metabolism slows down - this is due to the predominance of slow-wave sleep, when there is a significant decrease in glucose consumption by the brain and a decrease in its use by peripheral tissues. In the second half of the night, when light phases of sleep prevail and awakenings occur more often, these processes are activated again. During the slow-wave sleep phase, the authors believe that the secretion of growth hormone (somatotropin) is activated. This hormone ensures tissue repair, stimulates protein synthesis, cell regeneration, muscle growth and strengthening the immune system. Long-term sleep deprivation can reduce nighttime secretion of somatotropin, which negatively affects recovery processes.

The key role in the regulation of energy balance, according to [11], belongs to the hormones leptin and ghrelin. Leptin is a satiety hormone that helps maintain energy balance by reducing food intake and increasing energy expenditure. Ghrelin, on the contrary, is known as the "hunger hormone". Its level increases before eating, decreases sharply after it, and then gradually returns to its original values.

It has been found [12] that the secretion of leptin and ghrelin has daily fluctuations that are synchronized with each other: both hormones decrease during the night and reach their lowest level approximately between 8:00 and 10:00 in the morning. Thus, sleep disturbance can lead to an imbalance of leptin and ghrelin due to a shift in circadian rhythms, which can cause a disruption in metabolism and maintenance of homeostasis of the body as a whole.

Studies by a number of authors [13] have shown that during sleep the body actively repairs damaged

cells, regulates hormonal balance and restores energy resources necessary for further work. Violation of the duration or quality of sleep leads to a decrease in the efficiency of these processes, causing inflammatory reactions, a decrease in the immune response and metabolic disorders.

CONCLUSION

Thus, sleep is accompanied by a change in a number of physiological processes, tissue regeneration, protein synthesis and the release of a number of hormones necessary to ensure homeostasis of the human body. And, as a result, serve as the basis for the physical, emotional and psychological recovery of the body. The phases of REM and deep sleep complement each other, which helps the body adapt to stress, reduces the risk of injuries and increases the overall efficiency of recovery. As a result of physiological sleep, anxiety levels decrease, mood stabilizes, and motivation improves. During deep sleep phases, biochemical transformations are significantly activated, which contribute to memory consolidation, emotional stabilization, and processing of information received during the day during the REM sleep phase.

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